

Upland soil was sandy loam (Oxisol) with pH H₂O (1:1) 4.9, 4.3 kg Bray I's P/ha, 67 kg Bray I's K/ha, 105 kg total P/ha; 0.78% organic C, and CEC 10.2 meq/100 g. Inland valley swamp soil was clay loam (Typic Tropaquept) with pH H₂O (1:1) 4.2, 5.3 kg Bray I's P/ha, 74 kg Bray I's K/ha, 110 kg total P/ha, 2.4% organic C, and CEC 18.3 meq/100 g.

At the upland site, rice seeds were drilled 0.2 m apart in three 5-m-long rows/variety. At the inland valley swamp site, 21-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 2-3 seedlings/hill, 0.15- × 0.20-m spacing, in three 5-m-long rows/variety. Fertilizer was 60 kg N as urea, 32 kg K as muriate of potash at the upland site, and 40 kg N and 32 kg K/ha on the inland valley swamp. P was applied at 25 kg/ha, as appropriate.

In the uplands, 30 *O. glaberrima* and 10 *O. sativa* varieties showed tolerance for low P; in the inland valley swamps, 20 *O. glaberrima* and 11 *O. sativa* accessions showed tolerance (Table 1). These results indicate *O. glaberrima*

Table 1. Rice germplasm materials tolerant of low available P in Sierra Leone.^a

Rice accessions	Upland				Inland valley swamp			
	T	MT	S	Total	T	MT	S	Total
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	30	20	20	72	20	20	30	70
<i>O. sativa</i>	10	15	47	72	11	18	51	80
Total	40	35	69	144	31	38	81	150

^aT = tolerant (90-100%), MT = moderately tolerant (80.90%), S = susceptible (less than 80%).

Table 2. Correlations between tolerance for low available P and some plant characters.^a

Tolerance vs	Upland		Inland valley swamp	
	<i>O. gla.</i> ^b	<i>O. sat.</i> ^b	<i>O. gla.</i> ^c	<i>O. sat.</i> ^d
a. tiller no. at maximum tillering	0.80**	0.75**	0.68**	0.62**
b. panicles/m ²	0.58**	0.49**	0.45**	0.40**
c. plant height	0.21 ns	0.23 ns	0.17 ns	0.22 ns
d. duration	-0.62**	-0.59**	-0.63**	-0.59**
e. panicle weight	0.66**	0.71**	0.59**	0.75**
f. phosphorus content in grains	0.72**	0.64**	0.48**	0.46**

^aSignificant at the 1% (**) level. ns = not significant. ^bn = 72. ^cn = 70. ^dn = 80.

varieties have greater tolerance for low available P than *O. sativa* varieties. These accessions will be used in breeding for tolerance for low available P.

Tolerance for low available P correlated significantly with tiller production, panicles/m², panicle weight, and days to 50% flowering (Table 2). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

VX-83, a promising very short-duration rice variety in Vietnam

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Very short-duration rice varieties are important for intensifying farming systems in Vietnam and expanding the areas of winter crops such as maize, sweet potato, soybean, potato, and vegetables.

In 1985 we used diallel crossing method to estimate the combining ability of some rice varieties and selected the promising cross-combination line 64-8-3. It matures in 95-100 d, has semidwarf stature, and is tolerant of lodging, drought, and submergence. It is a high-tillering plant type, with yields of 6-8 t/ha, 1,000-grain weight 27-28 g, resistance to major diseases and pests, and high grain quality. Line 64-8-3 was named as rice variety VX-83 and recommended for production.

VX-83 was selected from the cross IR8/IR22-XL//IR19746-11-33 (or CN2).

Performance of VX-83 in replicated yield trials at nine locations in 1988-89 is given in Table 1. VX-83 has the same duration as IR19746-11-33 and CN2 (check 2), and is about 18-22 d earlier

than IR8423 (check 1). VX-83 yields were higher than those of other entries. It has better resistance to major diseases and pests (Table 2).

VX-83 is recommended for late spring, early summer, and summer-autumn rice crops. ■

Table 1. Yields of VX-83 and other rices at 9 locations in 1988-89.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)								
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
IR8423 (check 1)	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.3	4.3	4.4	4.6	4.6	4.6
VX-83	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.4	4.3	4.5	4.6	4.6	4.6
C662083	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.1	4.0	4.0	4.4	4.4	4.4
IR19746-11-33 (check 2)	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.7	3.7	3.6	3.9	3.9	3.9

Table 2. Resistance of VX-83 to diseases and pests.

Entry	Reaction ^a to			
	Brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 2	Bacterial blight	Sheath blight	Blast
IR8423 (check 1)	1	2	7	5
VX-83	1	1	3	3
C662083	3	1	3	3
IR19746-11-33 (check 2)	1	2	7	5

^a1 = resistant, 3 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible.